

PREVALENCE AND DISTRIBUTION OF VANCOMYCIN INTERMEDIATE, VANCOMYCIN RESISTANT AND HETEROGENEOUS VANCOMYCIN INTERMEDIATE *S. AUREUS* IN CLINICAL ISOLATES: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Introduction: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) caused various diseases and created a global crisis to public health. The disease caused by MRSA are treated with vancomycin. Initially vancomycin become a gold standard treatment for the diseases caused by MRSA but after some time prevalence of heterogeneous vancomycin intermediate *S. aureus*, vancomycin intermediate *S. aureus* and vancomycin resistant *S. aureus* (hVISA, VISA and VRSA) has been emerged from different part of the world. **Methods:** A extensive search was conducted with the help of electronic databases, like as PubMed, Scopus and Google Scholar, to identify similar studies to the hVISA, VISA and VRSA. The search strategy employed a combination of keywords and medical terminologies associated with *Staphylococcus aureus* and antibiotic vancomycin. **Result:** This systematic review provide overall prevalence of hVISA was 5.2% in 32180 MRSA strains, the prevalence of VISA 3.8% in 27472 MRSA strains and VRSA prevalence was 6.69% in 4815 MRSA strains. The incidence of hVISA was 1.88% before 2000, 6.89% in 2001-2010, 11% in 2011-2020 and 10.78% in 2021-2023. VISA prevalence was 0.73% before 2000, 2.37% in 2001-2010 and 10.82% in 2011-2020. VRSA was not isolated before 2000, the prevalence of VRSA was 1.8% in 2001-2010 and 7.97% in 2011-2020. **Conclusion:** The incidence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA has been elevated in last few years mainly in Asia continent than Europe/America. This systematic review provide the prevalence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA and suggest to isolate this type of *S. aureus* and control community and hospital associated infections.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus Aureus*, VISA, hVISA, VRSA and MRSA.

INTRODUCTION

Staphylococcus aureus, a gram-positive cocci and cause both community-associated and nosocomial-associated infections.⁽¹⁾ *S. aureus* are colonized around 25–30% of healthy persons on their skins, anterior nares and axilla, at which *S. aureus* present like a commensal and don't cause any illness in immunocompetent individuals.⁽²⁾ Whereas, *S. aureus* may cause various type of infections through bloodstream or penetrating the internal tissues and causes different types of clinical presentation which range from mild infections to serious and life-effecting pervasive infections like as boils, abscesses, impetigo, cell destruction, infections in hair follicles and sepsis,⁽³⁾ and these infections become challenging for public health issue because the emergence and dissemination of antibiotics resistant strains, like as, methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA).⁽⁴⁾ Methicillin resistance in *S. aureus* strains is due to the

alteration of penicillin binding protein to penicillin binding protein 2a and presence of *mecA* gene in the bacterial chromosome, these proteins and enzymes help to the bacterial cell wall for crosslinking the peptidoglycans. PBP2a and enzymes both showing low affinity to β -lactams antibiotics group and causing resistance to this type of antibiotics category.⁽⁵⁾ Vancomycin is the drug of choice for treating the MRSA infections. But unluckily there has been an indiscriminate use of vancomycin for human and as well as in the area of veterinary for other infections resulted in the development of hVISA, VISA and VRSA.⁽⁶⁾ However, the first case of VISA was isolated from Japan in 1997⁽⁷⁾ and first VRSA strain was isolated from Michigan (USA) in 2002. After some time, VRSA were reported from Oceania, Europe and other Asian countries.⁽⁸⁾ Out of these two strains of *S. aureus* there is a strain also present which is called hVISA which has the vancomycin MIC in the susceptible range ($< 2\mu\text{g/ml}$) but contains some vancomycin intermediate cells like as one vancomycin intermediate cell per 10^5 to 10^6 vancomycin sensitive cells.⁽⁹⁾ In last few years, there have been many articles, reports, systematic reviews or meta-analysis published from a hospital or individual countries and shows prevalence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA. The systematic review conducted by Zhang et al. on the epidemiology of hVISA and VISA was published over 7 years ago.⁽¹⁰⁾ A systematic review also conducted by Wu et al. and observe the diagnostic importance and outcomes of VRSA.⁽¹¹⁾ This review goal to provide the pattern of antibiotics resistance and prevalence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA against *S. aureus* which is carried out by identifying the gene responsible for antibiotics resistance and combat this growing problem. This systematic review give clue to the clinician for empirical therapy and better management of patients and it is beneficial for future research in the field of antibiotics resistance.

METHODOLOGY

Search Criteria

The searching criteria for identifying the appropriate articles related to this systematic review was developed by author. The searching is depend on the characteristics of VISA, hVISA and VRSA infections. These strains causing the infections and isolated from whole world and become a major public health problem in this review the most common type of gene causing vancomycin resistance was reviewed. Electronic database like as Scopus, PubMed and Embase were used to search the appropriate articles. And some other online database such as Google Scholar and PubMed also utilized to identify the appropriate articles. The duration for the search was from 1997 to 2023 set to track maximum of the strains after the first isolation in 1997 of vancomycin intermediate *S. aureus* to till now. Some of the studies and worldwide case reports were reviewed which give a holistic view of the infections. Case reports presented by clinicians, microbiologists, and public health practitioners and published we get original data through it.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies recognize in the literature search were checked by title and abstract. The articles and reports with relevant title and abstracts were checked carefully. The selection and rejection criteria for the studies were depend on the author criteria. The author provide selection criteria of the studies were given as: 1) Studies which give appropriate original data about the incidence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA, 2) Articles and peer reviewed which included all MRSA strains randomly, 3) Studies employed

publicly accepted methods for the detection of hVISA, VISA and VRSA, 4) Articles included which were published only in English language. The rejection criteria of the studies were given below: 1) Articles that provide wrong data or overlapping, 2) Reviews and conference abstracts, 3) Articles excluded that contain less than 10 cases.

Data extraction

The following part were selected from each included study: Name of the first author, study conducted year, publishing year, name of continent, country name, total number of MRSA strains, source of specimen, isolates number of VRSA, VISA and hVISA, methods used for detection, the MIC of vancomycin data were collected.

Fig 1: Flowchart showing study selection

DATA ANALYSIS

The information were collected and categorized into groups of hVISA, VISA and VRSA strains. The information were further categorized into subgroups of continents. A differentiation between the genetic causes, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration, and AST was carried out. In this review we also observed, which antibiotics was most effective and common against these type of infections. This study giving a idea about the etiology of these strains, MIC, and vancomycin activity which can help to minimize the prevalence and spread of vancomycin resistant *S. aureus* strains, there are some limitations to this review. There are many cases in developing countries which is not reported due to the lack of resources to identify and treat these infections, limited knowledge, medical infrastructure and economic constraints. Even if the cases were identify and treated but not publish due to the absence of publications so can not track this type of strains.

RESULT

Literature search

Almost, most of the studies were observed from the duration of 1997 to 2023. The number of 530 studies were identified from Google Scholar, PubMed and Embase. Out of these studies, 408 studies were excluded due to title and abstract is not relevant. Remaining 122 studies were further screened on the bases of exclusion and inclusion criteria 30 studies more excluded. Therefore 92 studies were selected on the bases of inclusion and exclusion criteria which is showing in (Fig. 1). These 92 studies were selected from different continent 49 from Asia, 22 from Europe, 19 from America and 2 from Oceania.

hVISA, VISA and VRSA prevalence divide into different study periods:

The overall prevalence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA were 5.2% (95% CI 4.96-5.44), 3.8% (95% CI 3.58-4.03) and 6.69% (95% CI 5.98-7.39) respectively. During the different study period observed the variation in hVISA, VISA and VRSA prevalence in last few years, On the basis of study year these strains are categorized into four periods (before 2000, 2001–2010, and 2011–2020 and 2021-2023) were designated. Few articles which was not confirm to the study duration were not included in this analysis.

Table 2, shows the incidence of hVISA increase gradually from 1.88% (95% CI 1.64-2.11) of 12941 MRSA strains in 15 studies before 2000 to 6.89% (95% CI 0.38-7.27) of 16663 strains in 40 studies from 2001-2010, 11.00% (95% CI 9.74-12.26) of 2372 strains in 10 studies from 2011-2020 and reach to 10.78% (95% CI 6.53-15.04) of 204 MRSA strains in 1 study from 2021-2023. The prevalence of VISA was 0.73% (95% CI 0.54-0.92) of 7696 MRSA strains in 7 studies before 2000, 2.37% (95% CI 2.12-2.63) of 13621 MRSA strains in 26 studies from 2001-2010, 10.82% (95% CI 10.04-11.6) of 6155 MRSA strains in 10 studies from 2011-2020. The VRSA strains was not isolated before 2000. The incidence of VRSA was 1.8% (95% CI 0.97-2.62) of 1000 strains in 5 studies from 2001-2010, 7.97% (95% CI 7.97-8.83) of 3815 strains in 10 studies from 2011-2020.

Prevalence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA in various clinical specimens:

The MRSA strains were obtained from the various types of the clinical specimens but here the clinical samples were divided into two category. 1st category was obtained from only blood culture specimens and 2nd category isolates from all diagnostic specimens other than blood culture. All diagnostic specimens, including sputum, ET tip, pus, urine, body fluids etc. The prevalence of hVISA was 7.2% (95% CI 0.64-7.85) in 6312 strains in 20 studies reported from the blood culture sample, prevalence of hVISA is higher in blood culture sample as compare to all clinical samples which shows the prevalence of 4.71% (95% CI 4.45-4.97) in 25868 strains in 46 studies reported from all clinical samples. The prevalence of VISA was 3.04% (95% CI 2.54-3.54) in 4473 strains of MRSA in 7 studies reported from blood culture samples and which is lower than 3.95% (95% CI 3.7-4.2) in 22999 MRSA isolated from all diagnostic specimens in another 36 articles. The VRSA strains were not isolated from blood culture specimens and the prevalence of VRSA in all clinical samples was 6.68% (95% CI 5.99-7.39) in 4815 strains isolated from 15 studies.

Table 1: Characteristics of the eligible studies

Author name, publication year	Country, Continent	Time period of study	Organism isolated from	Methods use for detection	hVISA Prevalence%	VISA Prevalence%	VRSA Prevalence %	References
Keiichi et al. 1997	Japan, Asia	1996-1997	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	34/1149 (3.0)	-	-	(12)
Hideaki et al, 2007	Japan, Asia	1978-2005	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilometer-test	-	5/2446 (0.2)	-	(13)
Hui-min et al, 2007	Japan, Asia	1998-2005	Blood culture	PAP-AUC	2/20 (10)	-	-	(14)
Aminaka et al, 2009	Japan, Asia	1999	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	7/138 (5.1)	0/138 (0)	-	(15)
Hideaki et al, 2014	Japan, Asia	2008-2011	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	55/830 (6.5)	8/830 (1.0)	-	(16)
Samson et al, 1999	Hong Kong, Asia	1997-1998	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilometer-test	3/52 (5.8)	-	-	(17)
Suwanna et al, 2001	Thailand, Asia	1998-1999	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	5/155 (3.2)	-	-	(18)
Aroonlug et al, 2009	Thailand, Asia	2002-2003	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	4/533 (0.8)	-	-	(19)
Aroonlug et al, 2009	Thailand, Asia	2006-2007	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	8/361 (2.2)	3/361 (0.8)	-	(19)
Pawana et al,2014	Thailand, Asia	2010-2011	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	2/68 (2.9)	-	-	(20)
Mi-Na et al, 2000	Korea, Asia	1999/01-1999/08	All Diagnostic Specimen	PAP-AUC	59/3371 (1.8)	-	-	(21)
Mi-Na et al, 2002	Korea, Asia	1998/12-1999/08	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	24/3363 (0.7)	0/3363 (0)	-	(22)
Ki-Ho et al, 2012	Korea, Asia	2008-2010	Blood culture	Epsilometer-test	101/268(37.7)	-	-	(23)
Yong Rae et al, 2016	Korea, Asia	2012/04-2013/04	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	79/229 (34.5)	-	-	(24)
Wei-Yao et al, 2009	Taiwan, Asia	2001-2003	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	2/13 (15.3)	8/13 (61.5)	-	(25)
Po-Ren et al, 2010	Taiwan, Asia	2001-2002	All Diagnostic Specimen	MICbased	-	43/1500 (2.9)	-	(26)
C-M et al, 2010	Taiwan, Asia	2003/03-2003/08	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	7/1000 (0.7)	2/1000 (0.2)	-	(27)
Shang-Yi et al, 2012	Taiwan, Asia	2009/03-2009/12	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	5/62 (8.1)	-	-	(28)

Yasmeen et al, 2007	Israel, Asia	2003-2004	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	16/264 (6.0)	-	-	(29)
Yasmeen et al, 2009	Israel, Asia	2003-2006	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	27/223 (12.1)	-	-	(30)
Biswajit et al, 2008	India, Asia	2002-2005	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC & PCR-based	-	-	1/57 (1.8)	(31)
Floriana et al, 2010	India, Asia	2005-2007	All Diagnostic Specimen	BHI, MET	36/139 (25.9)	0/139 (0)	-	(32)
Rajendra et al, 2011	India, Asia	2003-2007	All Diagnostic Specimen	PCR-based	-	-	4/282 (1.40)	(33)
Venubabu et al, 2011	India, Asia	2008/03-2008/10	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC based PCR based	-	16/358 (4.5)	7/358 (1.9) 6/358 (1.7)	(34)
Shanmugarajet al, 2013	India, Asia	2009-2010	All Diagnostic Specimen	MHA	-	10/63 (15.9)	-	(35)
Debasmita et al, 2013	India, Asia	2009-2012	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilometer-test	-	545/1214 (44.9)	251/1214 (20.6)	(36)
Manu et al, 2013	India, Asia	2013	All Diagnostic Specimen	MHA	8/130 (6.1)	-	-	(37)
Surg et al, 2015	India, Asia	2010-2013	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	4/58 (6.9)	-	-	(38)
Mahadeo et al, 2017	India, Asia	2015-2016	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC-based	-	11/32 (34.4)	4/32 (12.5)	(39)
Kiranjeet et al, 2019	India, Asia	2016-2017	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC-based	-	19/162 (11.7)	4/162 (2.5)	(40)
Vinay et al, 2020	India, Asia	2010-2012	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC- based	-	53/115 (46.08)	7/115 (6.08)	(41)
Sreejisha et al, 2023	India, Asia	2019-2020	All Diagnostic Specimen	PAP-AUC	14/220 (6.4)	-	-	(9)
Nashra et al, 2019	India, Asia	2017-2018	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilometer-test	-	8/140 (5.7)	2/140 (1.3)	(42)
Wenjia et al, 2009	China, Asia	2005-2007	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	26/200 (13.1)	1/200 (0.5)	-	(43)
Hongbin et al,2011	China, Asia	2005-2008	All Diagnostic Specimen	PAP-AUC	62/559 (11.1)	0/559 (0)	-	(44)
Wang et al,2013	China, Asia	2007-2009	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	25/122 (20.5)	-	-	(45)
Guo et al, 2013	China, Asia	2012/06-2012/12	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC based	-	1/1790 (0.06)	-	(46)

Jin et al,2023	China, Asia	2019-2021	All Diagnostic Specimen	PAP-AUC	22/204 (10.9)	-	-	(5)
Horieh et al, 2008	Iran, Asia	2006-2007	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC-based	-	3/164 (1.8)	1/164 (0.6)	(47)
Farhad et al, 2016	Iran, Asia	2009-2011	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	-	-	23/250 (9.2)	(48)
Yousefi et al, 2017	Iran, Asia	2014-2015	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC & PCR based	-	-	2/30 (6.7)	(49)
Marjan et al, 2017	Iran, Asia	2014-2017	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC & PCR based	-	2/1789 (0.1)	4/1789 (0.2)	(50)
R.K.C et al, 2009	Singapore, Asia	2005-2006	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	3/56 (5.4)	-	-	(51)
Norazah et al, 2012	Malaysia, Asia	2009/01-2009/12	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	2/43 (4.7)	-	-	(52)
Siti Roszilawati et al, 2012	Malaysia, Asia	2009/02-2009/05	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	7/320 (2.2)	-	-	(53)
Kaleem et al, 2012	Pakistan, Asia	2012	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	6/347 (1.7)	-	-	(54)
Jae-Hoon et al, 2004	Asia	1997-2000	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	58/1357 (4.3)	-	-	(55)
Meera et al, 2021	Nepal, Asia	2018/07-2018/12	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	-	15/45 (33.3)	5/45 (11.1)	(6)
Niranjan et al, 2023	Nepal, Asia	2019/12-2020/06	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC based	-	4/38 (10.5)	2/38 (5.2)	(56)
Geisel et al, 1999	Germany, Europe	1992-1998	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	7/85 (8.2)	-	-	(57)
Bierbaum et al, 1999	Germany, Europe	1997	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	2/367 (0.5)	-	-	(58)
Canton et al,1999	Spain, Europe	1997-1998	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	-	12/248 (4.8)	-	(59)
Azzam et al, 2006	Spain, Europe	2002-2004	All Diagnostic Specimen	MHA	-	-	5/139 (3.6)	(60)
Marchese et al, 2000	Italy, Europe	1997-1998	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	2/179 (1.1)	-	-	(61)
Reverdy et al, 2001	French, Europe	1998-1999	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	5/171 (2.9)	-	-	(62)
Frederic et al, 2003	France, Europe	1997-2002	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	13/48 (27.1)	-	-	(63)

Cartolano et al, 2004	France, Europe	2000	All Diagnostic Specimen	MHA	-	31/1070 (2.9)	-	(64)
Jerome et al, 2006	France, Europe	1983-2001	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	-	1/1445 (0.07)	-	(65)
Arnaud et al, 2006	France, Europe	1999-2000	All Diagnostic Specimen	MHA	11/329 (3.3)	-	-	(66)
Fabien et al, 2006	France, Europe	2001-2002	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	255/2300(11.1)	-	-	(67)
Sylvie et al, 2012	France, Europe	2007	All Diagnostic Specimen	MHA	12/20 (60.0)	-	-	(68)
Olivier et al, 2002	Belgium, Europe	1999/01-1999/12	Blood culture	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	4/2145 (0.1)	3/2145 (0.1)	-	(69)
Pierard et al, 2004	Belgium, Europe	2003	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	5/1002 (0.5)	1/1002 (0.1)	-	(70)
Nonhoff et al, 2005	Belgium, Europe	2001/01-2001/12	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	3/455 (0.7)	-	-	(71)
Banu et al, 2005	Turkey, Europe	1998-2002	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	46/256 (18.0)	0/256 (0)	-	(72)
Banu et al, 2013	Turkey, Europe	2009-2010	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	24/175 (13.7)	0/175 (0)	-	(73)
Deniz et al, 2021	Turkey, Europe	2018/04-2019/10	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	43/100 (43)	-	-	(74)
Margaret et al, 2007	Ireland, Europe	1998-2004	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	73/3189 (2.3)	-	-	(75)
Ilker et al, 2012	Switzerland, Europe	1995-2003	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	-	55/208 (26.4)	-	(76)
Vaudaux et al, 2012	Switzerland, Europe	2000-2008	All Diagnostic Specimen	MHA	-	13/57 (31.7)	-	(77)
Mlynarczyk et al, 2003	Poland, Europe	2002	All Diagnostic Specimen	PAP-AUC	5/103 (4.8)	0/103 (0)	-	(78)
Ariza et al, 1999	USA, America	1990-1997	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilon-meter-test	14/19 (73.3)	-	-	(79)
Susannah et al, 1999	USA, America	1997	All Diagnostic Specimen	MHA	-	4/630 (0.6)	-	(80)
Fridkin et al, 2003	USA, America	1999-2000	All Diagnostic Specimen	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	-	6/102 (5.8)	-	(81)
Amir et al, 2004	USA, America	2002/01-2002/12	Blood culture	Brain Heart Infusion Agar	3/22 (13.6)	-	-	(82)

Michael J et al, 2008	USA, America	1994-2002	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	27/356 (7.6)	8/356 (2.3)	-	(83)
Michael J et al, 2008	USA, America	2003-2007	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	76/917 (8.3)	3/917 (0.3)	-	(83)
Klaudia et al,2008	USA, America	2006-2007	All Diagnostic Specimen	Macromethod E-Test	2/982 (0.2)	3/982 (0.3)	-	(84)
Adina C et al, 2009	USA, America	1996-1997	Blood culture	MHA	8/61 (13.1)	-	-	(85)
Adina C et al, 2009	USA, America	2000-2001	Blood culture	MHA	5/55 (9.1)	-	-	(85)
Helio S et al, 2009	USA, America	2002-2006	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	36/268 (13.4)	-	-	(86)
Pastagia et al, 2009	USA, America	2002-2007	Blood culture	Epsilometer-test	45/699 (6.4)	118/699 (16.9)	-	(87)
Adina C et al, 2009	USA, America	2002-2003	Blood culture	MHA	37/187 (19.8)	-	-	(85)
Adina C et al, 2009	USA, America	2005-2006	Blood culture	MHA	21/186 (11.3)	-	-	(85)
Heather et al, 2010	Canada, America	1995-2006	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilometer-test	25/475 (5.3)	-	-	(88)
Adam M et al 2011	USA, America	2000-2008	Blood culture	Epsilometer-test	2/167 (1.2)	-	-	(89)
Riad et al, 2011	USA, America	2002-03, 2005-06	Blood culture	Macromethod E-Test	30/371 (8.1)	6/371 (1.6)	-	(90)
Cory et al, 2012	USA, America	2007-2008	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC-based	9/77 (11.7)	22/77 (28.6)	-	(91)
Anthony M et al, 2014	USA, America	2002-2013	All Diagnostic Specimen	PAP-AUC	38/266 (18.8)	-	-	(92)
Alessandro Conrado et al, 2014	Brazil, America	2009-2013	All Diagnostic Specimen	Epsilometer-test	12/124 (9.7)	-	-	(93)
Patrick GP et al, 2004	Australia, Oceania	2001-2002	Blood culture	Epsilometer-test	5/53 (9.4)	0/53 (0)	-	(94)
Kylie C et al, 2009	Australia, Oceania	2005/03- 2005/12	All Diagnostic Specimen	MIC-based	56/117 (47.9)	2/117 (1.7)	-	(95)

*PAP-AUC: Population Analysis Profile-Area under the curve, MHA: Mueller Hinton Agar, MIC: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration, PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction,

Prevalence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA at different geographical regions

hVISA, VISA and VRSA varied prevalence in different geographical regions in this analysis. The incidence of hVISA was 4.83 % (95% CI 0.33-5.16) of 16024 MRSA isolates in 33 studies from Asia/Oceania, and 5.57 % (95% CI 5.22-5.92) of 16156 strains in 33 articles from Europe/America continents. The prevalence of VISA was 4.56 % (95% CI 4.25-4.88) in 16629 strains of MRSA isolates in 25 articles from Asia/Oceania, and 2.64 % (95% CI 0.3-2.94) in 10843 MRSA strains isolated from 18 articles from Europe/America continent. However 6.78 % (95% CI 6.06-7.5) of 4676 MRSA strains were VRSA isolated in 14 studies from Asia/Oceania compared with 3.56 % (95% CI 0.5-6.7) of 139 MRSA strains in 1 study from Europe/America.

Table 2: hVISA, VISA and VRSA strains prevalence based on duration of study, origin of study, and selection of isolated organism

Strain	Category	Sub category	No. Studies	Isolated hVISA/ VISA/ VRSA	Total no. of strains	Prevalence(%) (95% CI*)
hVISA	Overall		66	1674	32180	5.2 (4.96-5.44)
	Study period	Before 2000	15	243	12941	1.88 (1.64-2.11)
		2001-2010	40	1148	16663	6.89 (0.38-7.27)
		2011-2020	10	261	2372	11.00 (9.74-12.26)
		2021-2023	1	22	204	10.78 (6.53-15.04)
Continent	Asia-Oceania	33	774	16024	4.83 (0.33-5.16)	
	Europe-America	33	900	16156	5.57 (5.22-5.92)	
Clinical sample	Blood Culture	20	455	6312	7.2 (0.64-7.85)	
	All Diagnostic sample	46	1219	25868	4.71 (4.45-4.97)	
VISA	Overall		43	1045	27472	3.80 (3.58-4.03)
	Study period	Before 2000	7	56	7696	0.73 (0.54-0.92)
		2001-2010	26	323	13621	2.37 (2.12-2.63)
		2011-2020	10	666	6155	10.82 (10.04-11.6)
		2021-2023	-	-	-	-
Continent	Asia-Oceania	25	759	16629	4.56 (4.25-4.88)	
	Europe-America	18	286	10843	2.64 (0.3-2.94)	
Clinical sample	Blood Culture	7	136	4473	3.04 (2.54-3.54)	
	All Diagnostic sample	36	909	22999	3.95 (3.7-4.2)	
VRSA	Overall		15	322	4815	6.69 (5.98-7.39)
	Study period	Before 2000	-	-	-	-
		2001-2010	5	18	1000	1.8 (0.97-2.62)
		2011-2020	10	304	3815	7.97 (7.11-8.83)
		2021-2023	-	-	-	-
Continent	Asia-Oceania	14	317	4676	6.78 (6.06-7.5)	
	Europe-America	1	5	139	3.56 (0.50-6.7)	
Clinical sample	Blood Culture	-	-	-	-	
	All Diagnostic sample	15	322	4815	6.68 (5.99-7.39)	

*Confidence Interval

DISCUSSION

The elevated prevalence of *S. aureus* strains with resistance to methicillin and reduced sensitivity to vancomycin has making a more dreadful situation and concern for discovery of new antibiotic agents that kill the resistant strains. Emergence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA increase because the indiscriminate use of vancomycin.⁽⁴²⁾ However, the studies included in this analysis shows that the treatment failure rate of vancomycin had increased. Havaei et al, 2012 studied 171 strains, out of these strains 97.07 % strains shows the MIC within susceptible range (<2µg/ml) and called the VSSA and 5 (2.93%) strains shows the MIC value between 4-8µg/ml and called VISA strains.⁽⁹⁶⁾ Amberpet et al, 2019 reported 500 MRSA strains which were isolated from various ward, and they defined the treatment failure of vancomycin and increase mortality of patients. Out of 500 MRSA strains 66 (13.2%) MRSA strains are hVISA which is detected by BHIV4 method. Prevalence of hVISA is higher as compare to this study.⁽⁹⁷⁾

In this systematic review we noted that some of the studies reported the MIC of *S. aureus* strains were higher in Brain Heart Infusion medium as compare to the Mueller hinton medium. This type of MIC results suggest that the vancomycin intermediate level of *S. aureus* is directly depend on the nutritional status of the medium. BHI medium fulfilled of nutrition and give better nutrition to the *S. aureus* which is similar to the medium of human body, but the MH medium does not provide the enough nutrition to the bacterial growth and MH medium act as a external environment due to lack of the nutrient as compare to BHI medium. Therefore, it is the main reason for detection of hVISA strains we used BHI medium and this medium provide better nutrition to the strains and grow easily.⁽⁹⁸⁾ Sreejisha et al 2023 studied 220 MRSA strains which is obtained from diabetic and non-diabetic patients, out of these MRSA strains 14 (6.4%) were hVISA. The rate of hVISA among MRSA isolated from diabetic and non-diabetic were 9.0% and 3.1% respectively.⁽⁹⁾

If MRSA or VRSA once established in hospital, then it will become difficult to clear off these strains and environment of the hospital may act as a source of hospital acquired infections in the future. So as soon as possible detection of these strains and genes which is responsible for antibiotic resistance such as van and mec gene would be a useful technique for the identification of these strains and help in the prevention and control of their spread.⁽⁶⁾

CONCLUSION

This systematic review highlights the emergence of hVISA, VISA and VRSA among the different geographical areas. The incidence of these strains has been elevated in last few years specially in Asia/Oceania as compare to Europe/America. The most prevalent of genes which is associated with VRSA and MRSA were vanA and mecA gene respectively. Other than these genes some genes also found in studies like as vanB and mecC genes which is responsible for antibiotics resistance. Prescribed antimicrobial treatments to the patients carefully by the clinicians and do not indiscriminate use of antimicrobial agent, detection of these type of strains are needed for preventing further emergence and dissemination of hVISA, VISA and VRSA strains.

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